

A Simple Receiver Design for Spectrally Efficient Frequency

Division Multiplexing (SEFDM)

10.5281/zenodo.14048181

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WIRELESS WORLD
RESEARCH FORUM

WWR50 Meeting
10-11 January, 2024

Virtual

Electromagnetic Spectrum Challenges

- Global mobile data traffic has exploded during the last decade
- Increase in number of connected devices
- Mobile traffic will keep growing exponentially during the next few years
- Scarcity in the available traffic

Need for High Spectral Efficiency

- Spectral Efficiency: by increasing the number of bits that could be transmitted over a given amount of bandwidth.
- Spectral Capacity: by increasing the bandwidths of the frequency spectrum assigned for 5G.
- Spectral reuse: by increasing the number of cells per unit area to densify the network in order to apply frequency reuse.
- MIMO

OFDM Limitations

- In addition to the advantages of the OFDM waveform, it has its own disadvantages that originated directly from the orthogonal nature of the waveform itself
- LTE system used 10% of the available spectrum as a frequency guard band to reduce the effect of Out Of Band Emission (OOBE) [1]
- The orthogonality of the OFDM waveform is also a constraint against achieving a higher spectral efficiency

Spectrally Efficient Frequency Division Multiplexing (SEFDM)

- More saving in BW
- Benefits of Orthogonal Frequency Division Multiplexing
- SEFDM as a non-orthogonal multicarrier technique

OFDM vs SEFDM

The SEFDM Challenges

- High complexity receiver design [4]
- Shannon capacity limit for the multi-carrier signal [5]

$$C \leq \frac{1}{\alpha} W \log_2 \left(1 + \frac{P_S}{P_N + P_{ICI}} \right)$$

Modeling the SEFDM Signal

$$R(f) = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{n=0}^{N-1} X_n V(f - F_n) + n(f) \quad (1)$$

For $0 < f < \infty$, where $X_n = |X_n|e^{-j\theta_n}$ is the transmitted symbol, $F_n = f_0 + \frac{n}{T}(1 - \alpha)$, $n(f)$ is the noise, and $V(f) = T \text{sinc}(\pi T f) e^{-j\pi T f}$, while T is the symbol duration, N is the number of subcarriers, and f_0 is the frequency of the first subcarrier.

Modeling the SEFDM Signal

By letting $F_n = f_0 + \frac{n}{T} (1 - \alpha)$, where α is the compression rate, it is obvious that for $\alpha = 0$ the signal $R(f)$ will be an OFDM signal. At any frequency f_k

$$R(f_k) = \frac{1}{2} \mathbf{X} \mathbf{V}_k + \mathbf{n} \quad (2)$$

Where

$$\mathbf{X} = [x_0 e^{j\theta_0} \quad x_1 e^{j\theta_1} \quad \dots \quad x_{N-1} e^{j\theta_{N-1}}],$$
$$\mathbf{V}_k = [V(f_k - F_0) \quad V(f_k - F_1) \quad \dots \quad V(f_k - F_{N-1})]^T$$

Modeling the SEFDM Signal

By taking $k = 0, 1, \dots, N - 1$ the vector \mathbf{R} and the matrix \mathbf{V} can be constructed such that each column is \mathbf{V}_k for every k , equation 2 can be written as follow:

$$\mathbf{R} = \frac{1}{2} \mathbf{XV} + \mathbf{n} \quad (3)$$

By sampling the received signal \mathbf{R} at the receiver, according to Nyquist the signal spectrum will be repeated in frequency domain and centered at each F_s

Modeling the SEFDM Signal

Using a higher sampling frequency

The vector \mathbf{R} could be obtained by taking the FFT for the received signal.

$$\begin{bmatrix} R(f_0) \\ R(f_1) \\ \vdots \\ R(f_{N-1}) \end{bmatrix}^T = \frac{1}{2} \begin{bmatrix} x_0 e^{j\theta_0} \\ x_1 e^{j\theta_1} \\ \vdots \\ x_{N-1} e^{j\theta_{N-1}} \end{bmatrix}^T \begin{bmatrix} v_{0,0} & v_{0,1} & \cdot & \cdot & v_{0,N-1} \\ v_{1,0} & v_{1,1} & \cdot & \cdot & v_{N-1} \\ \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot \\ \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot \\ v_{N-1,0} & v_{N-1,1} & \cdot & \cdot & v_{N-1,N-1} \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} n_0 \\ n_1 \\ \cdot \\ \cdot \\ n_{N-1} \end{bmatrix}^T \quad (4)$$

$$\mathbf{X} = \frac{1}{2} \mathbf{R} \mathbf{V}^{-1} + \mathbf{n} \mathbf{V}^{-1} \quad (5)$$

The SEFDM De-Modulator

Figure 1: Simple De-modulator design for receiving the SEFDM signal.

The SEFDM Performance

Figure 2: De-modulator BER performance for BPSK with 128 subcarriers for different values of α

The Matrix Inevitability Problem

Figure 3: The V matrix condition number for different value of alpha.

Applying the concept to OFDM

- $f_k = f_0 + \frac{k}{T} + \left(\frac{p}{T}\right)$ for $k=0,1, \dots, N-1$

The Matrix V for OFDM

Figure 4: The V matrix condition number for different value of ρ .

The Performance for different p

Figure 5: The BER performance for different value of p for QAM 64, 128 SC.

Conclusion

- 10% of the spectrum could be freed by using $\alpha = 0.1$ with a little degradation in BER performance.
- condition number of the matrix increases as the value of α increases.
- the results show that the system is working
- Better results depends on Matrix

Referance

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